

Prepare the final Draft for a poetry book in Spanish

Preparing the final Draft for a poetry book in Spanish

Final Paper

PM140 -Introduction to Project Management

LDS Business College

Table of Contents

Project Management Plan Purpose	3
Project Description...	3
Project Objectives	3
Project Deliverables	3
Project Scope Statement	4
Project Scope Management	5
Project Human Resource Management	5
Project Roles and Responsibilities	5
Project Quality Management	6
Project Communications Management	7
Project Procurement Management	8
Recommendations	8
Appendix A- Project Charter ...	9
Appendix B-Scope	10
Appendix C-Change	11
Appendix D-Schedule	12
Appendix E-Human Resources	12
Appendix F-Budget	13
Appendix G-Risk...	13

Project Management Plan Purpose

General Information

Project Name: Preparing the final Draft for a poetry book in Spanish

Project Manager: Mafer Herrera

Project Sponsor: Angel Investor

Time: 4 months

Budget: \$1000

Objective of the Project

Since I love writing and one of my personal goals is to write a book, my project will be to prepare the final draft for a poetry book in order to present it to an editor in the coming years. I think because it is a personal project, the benefits will be personal as well.

Project Deliverables

This is any measurable and verifiable product that is made to complete a project or part of a project. Deliverables help to define the scope of the project and the progress of the work in the project must be measured by monitoring the progress in the deliverables.

Deliverable / Milestone

- Set up schedule
- Prepare material
- Revise the material

See Appendix A

Success Criteria

- It will be finished on time
- The poems will be well made
- The material will pass all the filters
- The draft will be ready to present to an editorial in the coming years

Assumptions

- The people who will revise the project have experience in the field
- The project has the full support of the project sponsors
- Quality will be one of the priorities

Project Scope Statement

Items in Scope

- The draft will feature 20 poems
- The project will be completed in a period of 4 months
- The poems will be written in Spanish

Items not in Scope

- Personal circumstances that will affect the time to prepare the project
- Lacking of ideas and creativity
- The material wouldn't pass the filters.

Project Scope Management

Project Scope Management includes the processes necessary to ensure that the project includes all of the work required to complete it successfully. The main objective of the Project Scope Management is to define and control what is included and what is not included in the project. The project management will have meetings once a week. Some of the meetings will be via Skype. Any changes should be submitted for revision, debate, and approval of the project management team. There will also be daily communication via email, text, slack, etc. to assurance that every activity is going according to the established plan.

Project Human Resource Management

The workforce should be the most important part of a company and a project, which is why human resources management is important because it is in charge of valuing human capital. Another important function is budget control. This team is responsible for allocating the salaries of employees based on the labor market and their skills. The project Human Resource Management is Compound by the writer, project manager, revisers, and extra personnel as part of the risk plan.

See Appendix E

See Appendix H

Project Roles and Responsibilities

One of the biggest problems when starting a project, in which several professionals are involved, is the assignment of project roles. It is vital to clearly define the responsibilities of each one of the members of a project. In organizations with several simultaneous projects we must try to standardize these roles and responsibilities, so that they are homogeneous in all projects. Each member represents a different functionality and each member should have a recognized purpose.

We will inform about the operation of the project

- Stakeholder
- Project Manager

We will work hand in hand with

- Revisers
- Team members
- Sponsors

Roles and Responsibilities

Project Manager: In charge of the plan and execution

Stakeholders: the investors of the projects and they also help to make decisions

Reviewers: In charge of revising the content of the project

See Appendix E

Project Quality Management

MY QUALITY MANAGEMENT PLAN

QUALITY METRICS

Time. - 4 months

Scope. - Quality and complete the project on time

Budget. - \$1000 will cover everything needed for the project

MILESTONE LIST

Revisions of the manuscripts every week

Meetings via Skype once a week to evaluate the project

QUALITY MILESTONE TASK LIST

Revisions of the manuscripts every week

Ensure the quality of the poems

Check the grammar and the way the poems are written

Prepare the final Draft for a poetry book in Spanish

Revise the design

Meetings via Skype once a week to evaluate the project

Set goals to be more effective

Set calendar of activities

Revise the book content

QUALITY TOOLS

Meetings

Cause and Effect Diagram

Control chart

Check Sheet

Project Communications Management

One of the most important aspects of the project manager's work is the achievement of the objectives and the ease with which to advance the project.

Staffing Management Plan

Project Manager: Meetings via Skype once a week to evaluate the project

Stakeholders: Meetings via Skype once a week to evaluate the project

Reviewers: Revisions of the manuscripts every week

Project Procurement Management

Procurement needs

- Pens, pencils
- Notebooks
- Refreshments
- Computer

Buy Analysis

In this case because of time, everything would be purchased and since we are not using a huge amount of the materials that we need, it would be less expensive to buy. Everything that we need for the project such as pencils, notebooks, refreshments, etc. would be bought in the Dollar Tree. Everybody has their own personal computer, so it wouldn't be necessary to buy specific computers for the project.

Planning in advance

The backup plan is utilizing recycled paper and the computers of the LDSBC.

Recommendations

After all the analysis is done, it is suggested to execute this project, it would be convenient to review the risk points of the project. For that reason, it is also essential to conduct a market study in order to have greater knowledge and a complete vision, both internal and external factors.

Appendix A- Project Charter

Project Name:	Project Manager:
Prepare the final Draft for a poetry book in Spanish	Mafer Herrera
Today's Date:	Project Sponsor:
5/10/18	Mafer Herrera
Purpose / Objective of the Project (Provide a description of why we doing the project, project objectives and benefits)	
<p>Since I love writing, one of my personal goals is to write a book. My project will be preparing the final draft for a poetry book in order to present it to an editorial in the coming years. I think due it is a personal project, the benefits will be personal as well.</p>	
Success Criteria (How will you know if the project is successful after completion?)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It will be finished on time • The poems will be well made • The material will pass all the filters • The draft will be ready to present to an editorial in the coming years 	

Complete the following for all deliverables expected. Note the dates and estimated times are negotiated.

Deliverable / Milestone	Person/Team Responsible	Estimated End Date
Set up schedule	Mafer Herrera	5/15/18
Prepare material	Mafer Herrera	6/20/18
Revise the material	Mafer Herrera	7/10/18
	Editorial	7/10/18
	Editorial	7/10/18

Assumptions
(Complete the following for any assumptions required to satisfy the scope of the project)

1	The people who will revise the project have experience in the field
2	The project has the full support of the project sponsors
3	Quality will be one of the priorities

Prepare the final Draft for a poetry book in Spanish

Project Approval		Name Typed	Signed
5/10/18		Mafer Herrera	<i>Mafer Herrera</i>
Sponsor Approval		Name Typed	Signed
5/10/18		Mafer Herrera	<i>Mafer Herrera</i>
5/10/18		Angel Investor	

Appendix B-Scope

<p>Items in Scope</p> <p>(List all items that are to be included in the project)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The draft will feature 20 poems • The project will be completed in a period of 4 months • The poems will be written in Spanish
<p>Items not in Scope</p> <p>(List all items that are not being addressed during the project)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal circumstances that will affect the time to prepare the project • Lacking of ideas and creativity • The material wouldn't pass the filters. •

Appendix C-Change

CHANGE CONTROL OBJECTIVES

The main goal is to be ready and to know how to face different changes that the project could experience. It is also crucial to be able to work together as a team.

TYPES OF CHANGE

- Changes in the budget
- Changes in the team
- Change the content (add more poems, change the language, etc.)

CHANGE CONTROL BOARD

Name	Position/Title	CCB Role
Mafer Herrera	Project manager/ sponsor	Decision Maker
Angel Investor	Project sponsor	Decision Maker
Editorial	Reviewer	Counselor
Editorial	Reviewer	Counselor
Editorial	Reviewer	Counselor

ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

The responsibilities and decisions are shared between the members of the control board

Change Proposal	Include one more poem in english
Review	Schedule conflict
Reason for Change	I small introduction for a future english poetry book
Report	Change accepted
Change implementation	Project Manager and Sponsors
Result	Opportunity to test how it would be a poetry book in english
Authorized by	Project Manager
Date	5/21/2018

Mafer Herrera
Project Manager

CHANGE CONTROL PROCESS

The changes need to be evaluated before being approved by the members of the control board.

Appendix D-Schedule

Appendix E-Human Resources

Appendix F-Budget

Resource Name	Hours Required	Hourly Rate	Material Cost	Total Cost
PM Team	20	\$10.00		200
Labor	40	\$10.00		400
Materials <i>(needs to be broken out)</i>			50	50
Equipment				
Services				
Facilities	-	-	-	-
	-	-	-	-
	-	-	-	-
	-	-	-	-
Information Technology	-	-		
<i>Total Estimated Costs</i>				\$650
<i>Total Budget</i>				\$1000
<i>Difference</i>				\$350

Appendix G-Risk

Risk List								Student	21-Jul-18
Risk Title	Prob	Impact	P x I	Effect	Mitigation	Trigger Event	Contingency	Person Driving	
1. <i>Example:</i> Market crash within the next 8 months	5%	10	0.50	Example: Would derail the entire project	Example: Careful study and analysis of the Phoenix area market to reduce risk before proceeding	Example: Housing market crashes; real estate values plummet	Example: Sell as quickly as possible	Example: Project Manager	
2 Revisers canceled	5%	8	0.40	It would cause delays	Have substitutes	Don't get anybody else available or capable to help	Have a list of at least 5 people who are available to help	Project Sponsor	
3 Not finishing on time	3%	10	0.30	Not be able to present it	Planning and schedule time to finish everything	Having schedule conflicts	Specific hour to work on the project	Project Manager	

Prepare the final Draft for a poetry book in Spanish

4 Conflict of opinions	10%	6	0.60	Changes in the content	Have the (PM) as a mediator between the revisers	Having problems between the mediator and the members of the team	Have the (pm) or another person to be the mediator	Project Manager
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